

Morphological Constructions of Political Neologism in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study aims to reconnoiter neologism in the contemporary political setting of Pakistan. This study is based upon the procedure of creation of innovative lexicons in language with a distinct reference to political domain in Pakistan. For collection of the data, random sampling method is applied on two social media platforms; Twitter and YouTube. Frequently used new words in the recent political discourse are selected after keen annotations. Neologisms used for this research paper are especially checked by the researchers through twitter hashtags. For data analysis, neologisms have been categorized into two main categories,

morphological neologisms and semantic neologisms. They were further analyzed on the basis of the neologism formation process involved in each category. Results show that due to controlled media policy, metaphorical discussion or satirical analysis of political statements on electronic and social media raised the production of political neologism in Pakistan.

Key Words: Political neologism, Morphological construction, Coinage, Onomasiology Theory

1. Introduction

In 1988, a Russian linguist, Pavol Stekauer presented an approach of word-formation in English language, called lexico-semantics-Centered Approach. This approach is based upon an onomasiological model, which studies conceptual reflections of extra-linguistic realities in relation to their semantic features in new words formation by a speech community. This theory contends that the word-formation processes are as dynamic as syntactic processes are. According to Blank (2001), in lexical semantics, onomasiological theory studies different pathways through which a specific concept undergoes different linguistic changes and establishes its place in vocabulary of a speech community. The term onomasiology has its origin in Greek word, “onoma”, which means name. The approach reflects different procedural stages of word formation, from a concept to a concrete word. There is a definite link between extra-linguistic realities and different linguistic levels. Hoecki (1999) explicitly presented an onomasiological chain: object – conceptual, generalization – meaning – form. The aim of this study is to find Morphological formation in political neologisms in Pakistan political context through Onomaziological theory

Life of a language is determined by its speakers. The real owners/heirs of a language are the native speakers who may use the language both in conventional as well as in non-conventional settings.

They repeatedly the words, which sound good to them and discard the words, they find inappropriate in their everyday discourse. Furthermore, a language is kept alive through the speakers' creativity by coining new words or using existing words in new or unique connotations. This leads to the formation of numerous new words. This process of formation of new words is referred to as 'neologism'. This research focuses on the formation of new words in political discourse of Pakistan in recent years.

Political neologism is commonly found in Pakistani electronic, print and social media as political happenings concern a common man and are being discussed a lot by whole nation on every platform. Neologism occurs more often in societies undergoing through rapid change and with situation of easy and quick exchange of information (Zailani, 2019). Therefore, several new terms are coined by politicians in context of other degradation, self-praise, self-salience, and satire in order to exaggerate the situation. Political neologisms also occur in media domains to denote the political events or to converse the political crises in Pakistan by journalists, media anchors and political analysts as well as common social media users in their social media posts, twitter hashtags, YouTube thumbnails, slogans and placards displayed by protestants in different rallies and discussions in TV talk shows and YouTube Vlogs.

This research aims to investigate the types of neologisms and the process of word formation in political discourse of Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Neologism

The term neologism is referred to the newly coined words and phrases or the words created due to semantic shift in the use of exiting words (Nordquist, 2019). The use of a new word or expression of an established word in a new or different sense also turns out to be a neologism and phenomenon of this usage and introduction of such expressions into a language is termed as neology (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). According to Choi, "New words and phrases that are used commonly in speech but are not included in dictionaries are also regarded as neologisms" (Choi, 2006). Oxford dictionary also defines neologism as coining or use of a new word or expression. These new expressions can be produced through various word formation processes including abbreviation, back-formation, blending, borrowing, clipping, compounding, conversion and derivation and semantic shift of the existing words (The Oxford Dictionary of English Grammar, 2014).

2.2. Neologism in different domains

Neologism being a contemporary field of research has been investigated recently in different domains on top of which is information technology and social media. The boom of internet and technology produced a lot of neologisms which are focus of attention for linguists in contemporary researches on neologism. McDonald (2005).after a thorough research in this field, finds out that technology has contributed English language with a whole new suffix e- and produced hundreds of neologisms with this suffix. E.g. e-mail, e-commerce, e-marketing etc. Coining a neologism not only reflects innovative behaviors and practices of members of a society but also unveil and explain changes in the conventional way of living in this world and people's behavior and attitude towards these changes. Suffix e- and all the neologisms it produced reflects the e-revolution in marketing and business across the globe.

Social media is another platform where majority of the contemporary neologisms are produced. Handabura (2022) explored this area and investigated how the social media usage influences the

formation of neologism formed in English language. Various semantic and morphological neologisms found on Twitter and Facebook were investigated through their types, meaning and process of lexical formation. As findings of this study, lexical formation processes, derivation and compounding are responsible for morphological neologism while semantic neologism occurs due to the metaphorical use of existing lexemes.

Kadoch (2013) conducted a research to investigate neologism in journalistic discourse and frequency of their occurrences. He finds out that almost a half all the investigated neologisms were found in the journalistic texts alone. And frequency of this occurrence was far more than neologism occurring in spoken English and academic and fictional texts. (Kadoch, 2013). Neologism is not confined to the creation of new words only; it includes coining of new phrases or even new idioms. In Pakistani English Literature, Pakistani authors are creating local idioms through creative communication in English. One such example is Moni Mohsin's work, that created most of the neologism in Pakistani English literature in order to create humor and satirizing social practices (Riaz, 2021). Another research in Pakistani context was made by Tahir Rasool Tariq on neologism formation process in Urdu language. Famous TV show khabarnak was studied and analyzed for this purpose. The research finds out that most frequent word formation processes involved in the production of neologism in Urdu language were blending, compounding, affixation, acronym and coinage (Tariq, 2018).

2.3. Political Neologism

Political discourse is another domain where most of the neologisms occur. In fact, every political terminology was a neologism at some stage. Political neologism denotes the emerging of political notions in a society. Major shifts on political canvas or economic changes in a society create the demand for new terminologies to associates these political happenings with them (Jeffries, 2006). The conversation between government and society forms known neologism in political domain of that particular society. Furthermore, Hadi explored this specific domain of neologism and found that political neologism is bound in context of a specific society and would have no meaning in a different context (Hadi, 2019).

2.4. Coinage

Coinage is referred to the creation of an entirely new word in a language, however, inventing a new word from scratch is a rare phenomenon in lexical formation. The new terms are limited to the phenology of the particular languages (McGregor, 2009) and are often coined by combining existing words or by giving words new and unique suffixes or prefixes (Zailani, 2019). The coining of new terms involves further processes including onomatopoeia (formation of words based on the sound characteristics of their referent) and phonaesthesia which is the phonemic association with the meaning of certain lexicons (McGregor, 2009).

2.5. Morphological Neologisms

Neologisms are also formed through morphological changes in exiting words through compounding, blending, acronymy and borrowing. And the terms created through these word formation processes are called Morphological Neologisms (Pavel, 2001). Morphological neologisms are the new lexemes which result from an operation on the form and generally the meaning of a lexical base (Lombard, Huyghe, & Gyax, 2021).

2.6. Semantic Neologism

Semantic neologisms are formed due to semantic shift in the existing words without any change in their lexical formation. Meaning of an existing word can change over a period of time. Words may get additional connotations and the original meaning of the word may be suppressed due to this meaning expansion. (Wijaya & Yeniterzi, 2011). An opposite way of semantic shift in existing words is the meaning narrowing, in which a word is narrowed down to a specific sense, as the word doctor from holding a doctorate degree narrowed down to a person holding doctorate in the field of medicine only (McGregor, 2009).

3. Research Method and Methodology

This study is based upon qualitative method of research. Neologisms have been analyzed on the basis of morphological formation of newly coined terms and semantic shifts of older terms.

Table: 3.1

EXTRA-LINGUISTIC REALITY (POLITICAL CONTEXT)

3.1. Research Design

Political neologisms to be investigated under this research have been categorized into two main categories, morphological neologisms and semantic neologisms. The selected neologisms were double checked through twitter hashtags. Twitter hashtags were considered the authentication benchmark for the popular usage verification for a particular neologism.

3.2. Data Collection

The political neologisms are equally being used on mainstream media, but for data collection, instead of regular talk shows on TV channels, social media was preferred. As on social media freedom of expression is present in its true sense and the discourse available is as natural as possible.

3.3. Data Selected

Repeatedly used neologisms were selected on the basis of keen observation and verification from authentic dictionaries. Two major social media websites Twitter and YouTube were narrowed down to select data for this research including V-logs of senior known journalists on YouTube.

4. Analysis

This section comprises of qualitative analysis of the data under study. These neologisms were analyzed on the basis of word formation process of each class.

4.1. Morphological Neologisms

Operations seen in the formation of morphological neologisms in the selected data are blending, compounding, loan compounding (one term from second language and other form the local language), blending within a compound term, compounding within L2 lexemes, acronyming, slip of tongue, onomatopoeia and phonesthetic.

The term dhabarrdhoos coined by senior journalist Dr. Shahid Masoodis, is based on the process of onomatopoeia and phonesthesia as in Urdu language 'dh' sound is associated with heavy beats. e.g. dham, dhamak, dharraam, dhons, dhamki, dharrkan all refers to heavy voice or beat.

This research recommends to enter this political neologism, 'dhabarrdhoos' into Urdu dictionaries. As it is commonly being used in political context of Pakistan for more than 15 years and is accepted by common Urdu speakers of Pakistan.

Table 4.1: Morphological Constructions

List of words	Paradigmatic Syntagmatic Relations	Combinability Information	Morphological Process	Conceptual, Semantic, Onomological Levels
بد معاشیہ badma'ashiya	Syntagmatic	بد معاش+اشرفیہ badma'ash+ashraafiy a	Blending	Corrupt elites, who are part of status co.
دھبڑ دھوس dhabarr'dhoos	Paradigmatic	دھڑام + بھڑدھبڑ + بوس dharraam +habarrdabarr +bos	Coinage	A political system falling down with a banging noise.
لفافی Lifafi	Syntagmatic	لفافہ + صحافی lifafa+Safi	Blending	Journalist known for taking envelopes (lifafa) of bribe from politicians and ruling elite for not to report

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				against them in media.
خادم اعلیٰ khadim-e-aala	Syntagmatic	خادم+وزیر اعلیٰ Khadim+wazeer-e-aala	blending	A chief minister who believes in serving his people rather ruling them.
بغل بچے baghalbachey	Paradigmatic	بچے+بغل Baghal+ bachey	Compounding	The journalists who are favored by the ruling political party and do negative propaganda against opposition on government's demand.
معصومانہ سوال masoomana sawal	Paradigmatic	معصومانہ + سوال Masoomana+Sawal	Compounding	A quite pinching, direct question, someone might find it difficult to answer.
کانپیں ٹانگنا Kaampain taangna	Syntagmatic	کانپیں ٹانگنا Kaampain taangna		Shivering of legs in fear.
اسلامی ٹچ .. Islamic touch	Paradigmatic	اسلامی + ٹچ Islamic+touch	loan compounding	Using Islamic religion for personal or political gains.
کرائم منسٹر .. crime minister	Paradigmatic	کرائم + منسٹر crime+prime minister	loan compounding	A prime minister, who is corrupt.
آڈیولیکس .. audioleaks	Paradigmatic	آڈیو+لیکس audio + leaks	compounding	The phenomena of leaking personal phone calls or secret audio recordings of politicians, judges, media persons and

				other high professionals to blackmail them
زندگان nab'zadgan	نیب Syntagmatic	نیب + زندگان nab+zadgaan	Compounding	Refers to those who are facing corruption cases by NAB (National Accountability Bureau). This term is gradually gaining semantic shift towards an adjective for corrupt people.
حکومت imported hakoomat	امپورٹڈ Paradigmatic	امپورٹڈ + حکومت imported + hakoomat	Compounding	Government formed as a result of regime change with involvement of foreign interference in political matters of Pakistan.
مودتوا Modit'wa	Syntagmatic	ہندوتوا+مودی hindut'wa +modi (Blending)	RSS's extremism, racism and oppression against Muslims under fascist govt of Indian president Narindra Modi.	A satirical attack on Indian Prime Minister who acts against Pakistan

<p>سیاسی قبر <i>seyasi qabar</i></p>	<p>Paradigmatic</p>	<p>سیاسی + قبر seyasi+qabar (Compounding)</p>	<p>Political grave! It refers to political suicide by a politician who commits such a political blunder that may cost him end of his political career.</p>	<p>It refers to corruption in Pakistani politics such as 'horse tradig'</p>
<p>حقیقی آزادی <i>haqeeqi azadi</i></p>	<p>Paradigmatic</p>	<p>حقیقی + آزادی haqeeqi+azadi (Compounding)</p>	<p>Real freedom! The term refers to the Freedom, that is required to take national decisions in interest of Pakistani nation, neither in foreign interest, nor in corrupt ruling elites'.</p>	<p>An ideal spirit of liberty and freedom</p>
<p>بجلی بم</p>	<p>Paradigmatic</p>	<p>بجلی + پیٹرول بم</p>	<p>Electricity bomb!</p>	<p>It refers to increased load</p>

<i>bijli</i>	<i>bomb</i>		bijli+petrol bomb (Blending within L2 compound term)	It refers to Govt. announcement of increase in electricity prices.	of taxes on public, especially electricity bills.
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Discussion

A neologism is not born as neologism. Rather, a spontaneous utterance or a newly coined term when generally get accepted by the society and begin to be used by general public, only then it is recognized as a neologism.

Political neologisms are not as simple as other neologisms. As each political neologism has a series of political events and incidents involved in its context. Political neologisms produce in result of the metaphorical discourse to discuss political situation and giving implicit opinion about these situations to avoid wrath of the ruling elites or state actors. Neologisms discussed in this research also share deep background. For example, the term *خادم اعلیٰ* (khadim-e-aala) was coined by Mr. Shehbaz Shareef who served as CM Punjab for 11 years. In Urdu language, the term 'wazeer-e-aala' is used for chief minister and word 'khadim' means servant. Sareef preferred to be called khadim-e-ala instead of wazeer-e-aala.

Similarly, Ex-prime minister Imran Khan is known for coining new terms in his political speeches. He mret a denioc *بغل بچے* (baghal bachey) for journalists who are closed to his political opponents and are ,revoeroM .ytrap lacitilop dna evitarran lacitilop sih ,nahK narmI sdrawot desaib ylghih *لفافی* (lifafi) is another newly coined term for journalists who are assumed to take bribes from corrupt ruling elites to not to report against them in media. A journalist named 'Saleem Safi' is allegedly considered to be N-league's paid journalist, and the word 'Lifafa' (which refers to the envelop of bribe) has turned into the term lafafi as it rhymes with the word 'Safi'.

Another neologism in discourse of journalism is *معصومانہ سوال* (masoomana sawal). Literal meaning of this term would be 'innocent question'. But the neologism is used in totally opposite connotation. This nelogism was coined by famous Pakistani journalist 'Waseem Badami'. Initially it was name of a segment of his TV show, 'her lam'ha purjosh'. Where he would ask quite pinching and direct questions to the guests, which could be difficult to answer. Later this term was adopted by other journalists as well.

Neologism also produces new idioms or changes the existing ones. As the idiom *ٹانگیں کانپنا* (taangain kaanp'na) is changed into *کانپیں ٹانگنا* 'kaanpain taang'na'. This neologism was formed as a result of 'slip of tongue' by chairman PPP, Mr. Bilawal Zardari. In his long march against PTI government, Zardari uttered, "kaanpain taang rahi hain", instead of taangain kaamp rahi hain. In English this would exactly mean 'shegs are livering' instead of 'legs are shivering'. This slip of tongue was made fun of by social media users and became a twitter trend. Since then, the new form is used more than the original one specially in political discourse.

Likewise, another neologism born in a political rally, is *اسلامی ٹچ* (Islami touch). On 26 May, 2022 during Imran Khan's addressed to his long march rally, he was advised by former deputy speaker, Mr. Qasim Suri in a whisper, "خان صاحب تھوڑا اسلامک ٹچ بھی دے دیں" (Khan saab thorra Islamic touch

bhi dey dain) means, “sir please give some Islamic flavor as well.” this whisper was caught by mic and became headline in media against PTI for using religion for political gains. Now the term 'Islami touch' is used frequently as sarcasm in political talk shows, political tweets and even in comedy shows.

Conclusion

Neologisms are the newly coined words which have not been registered in the dictionaries yet but are in everyday usage of the speakers. And political neologism is referred to the neologisms produced in political discourse. Result shows that controlled media policy, metaphorical discussion or satirical analysis of political statements on electronic and social media, gave rise to the production of political neologism in Pakistan. Both morphological formation and semantic shift is involved in the creation of neologisms. Unlike past, current era of technology has made it easier to reach the origin of neologisms using digital platforms.

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